

Structured Missing Data

Grand Challenges in Learning from
Multi-Modal Data at Scale

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Turing-Roche Strategic Partnership

The Alan Turing Institute

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The Alan Turing Institute launches a strategic partnership with Roche to generate insights into disease, patient, and outcome heterogeneity using advanced analytics

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Turing-Roche Strategic Partnership

- Launched in June 2021- Roche is Turing's first pharmaceutical strategic partner
- 5-year collaboration guided by our **North Star:**

“To enable the generation of insights to better understand patient and disease heterogeneity and its relevance to clinical outcomes at an unprecedented level of precision in order to improve clinical care”

Agenda

1. **Introduction to missing data** | Theory & concepts
2. **Real-world example** | Structured missingness in an oncology clinico-genomic database
3. **Grand challenges** | Moving the field forward

Introduction to missing data | *Theory & concepts*

Missing data - framework

- The problem of missing data is encountered in many disciplines and impedes effective analysis of the data.
- The type of missing data can vary and some are more problematic than others.
- Suppose we denote our data set by \mathbf{X} which has \mathbf{n} rows (corresponding to \mathbf{n} individuals) and \mathbf{p} columns (\mathbf{p} variables).
- We can then define a missing data indicator matrix \mathbf{M} with the same dimensions of \mathbf{X} , with entries either **1** or **0**.
- If the *i th* row, *j th* column of \mathbf{X} is missing then we denote the corresponding entry of $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{1}$ otherwise $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{0}$.
- We can then decompose \mathbf{X} into its observed (\mathbf{X}_{obs}) and missing (\mathbf{X}_{mis}) parts.
- From this we can construct key concepts underpinning the different types of missing data.

Missing data - Missing data mechanism

- The **missing data mechanism** is the process that produces the missing values and is modelled as, $p(\mathbf{M}|\mathbf{X})$.
- If $p(\mathbf{M}|\mathbf{X}) = p(\mathbf{M})$, i.e. independent of X then we say missingness is **Missing Completely at Random (MCAR)**.
- If $p(\mathbf{M}|\mathbf{X}) = p(\mathbf{M}|\mathbf{X}_{\text{obs}})$ then we have **Missing at Random (MAR)**.
- If $p(\mathbf{M}|\mathbf{X})$ cannot be simplified any further then we have **Missing Not and Random (MNAR)**.
- Under MNAR the chance to be missing depends on the missing values themselves, and presents significant challenges to address.
- It is typical to assume that missingness is MAR, as that permits unbiased estimation/analysis methods.

Missing data - Missing data patterns

- The **missing data pattern** describes how the missing values are spread throughout the data
- There are two common decompositions, **monotone** and **non-monotone** patterns
- If the variables in the data can be ordered so that missing values occurring for individuals in variable **k** also imply they are missing values in all variables $> k$ this is a monotone pattern
- If the above does not occur then the pattern is non-monotone.

Monotone missing data pattern

Non-monotone missing data pattern

Missing data - Structured Missingness

- Structured missingness (SM) is a relatively newly coined term but is something that is being frequently encountered.
- SM arises when there is deemed to be some association between the *missing values themselves*.
- This structure could be strong/deterministic or weak/probabilistic.

Strong/deterministic SM

Weak/probabilistic SM

Structured Missingness - relevance

- Appetite for analysing large data sets, often combined from different sources, is constantly increasing.
- This is a classic setting for where SM can occur, e.g. when combining two different data sets measured on potentially individuals and variables that only partly overlap.
- Such an example illustrates how strong/deterministic SM could occur
- However, weak/probabilistic SM is also possible in many instances, e.g. batch failure.
- If a set of tests is being performed and one fails, then it may be more likely that other tests in the batch fail, but not necessarily guaranteed to happen.
- Roche's clinico-genomic database is a very comprehensive rich data source but will inevitably be affected by SM and provides a useful contextual example to discuss.

Real-world example | *Structured missingness in an oncology clinico-genomic database*

The Clinico-Genomic Database (CGDB) links Flatiron electronic health records with Foundation Medicine (FMI) comprehensive genomic profiling for tens of thousands of cancer patients in the U.S.

The linkage of information across distinct groupings and sources in the CGDB gives rise to **structured missingness**.

Observations can be missing across “blocks” of disparate information sets, e.g. by:

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Observations can be missing across “blocks” of disparate information sets, e.g. by:

Consider the “Prostate Specific Antigen” (PSA)

Important prognostic factors relevant for one group may not be measured, or possible to measure, in another.

Missing Prostate Specific Antigen (PSA) by cancer type and sex.

Genes of interest **may not be measured** in all genomic tests.

When it is desirable to learn across these data combined at scale, structured missingness presents an **immense learning challenge**...

Examples @ Roche:

- Making insights across cancer types → tumor-agnostic “pan-tumor” research
- Studying prognostic genomic features across patients → oncology biomarker research

More generally: this challenge will rise with the increasing development of multi-modal data sources.

What sorts of solutions are available to us? What challenges need to be addressed?

Grand challenges | *Moving the field forward*

We proposed 9 Grand Challenges in addressing and mitigating the effects of structured missingness when combining multi-modal data at scale.

Some challenges address **how to get started** with structured missingness (**SM**).

Defining SM

Rubin's missing data taxonomy is foundational.

What is it missing to incorporate concepts of structured missingness?

Exploring the geometry of SM

Certain structures of missingness can be known or obvious, like Prostate labs among females in the CGDB.

Can we uncover hidden, non-random patterns of missingness in data?

Can multivariate network science help characterize these patterns?

Imputing SM

In many cases, imputation does not make sense... for example, imputing Prostate labs for female patients!

How can we embed knowledge of missing data structures to inform novel imputation approaches?

Placeholder- additional challenges

Fairness

Certain groups are often under-represented in data sources.

Biomedical data sets are often mainly comprised of samples derived from Western or Caucasian individuals.

This can be viewed as SM, e.g. due to data collection practices.

Causal Inference

$$r_{XY} > r_{XY.Z} > 0$$

Determining causal relationships in the presence of missing values is known to be extremely challenging.

SM presents further complications that can bias causal inferences.

SM can itself be viewed causally, e.g. missingness in one variable may cause missingness elsewhere.

Design

Carefully constructing the design prior to conducting the experiment allows more efficient and robust analysis downstream.

Designs that account for the potential of SM to arise can help mitigate its effects, e.g. seek to redress any structural imbalances it causes in the data.

The Turing-Roche partnership has launched multiple projects in this space to develop **new solutions to SM challenges**

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Learning from data with structured missingness

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Using network science to quantify the geometry of “missingness”

Developing a coherent Bayesian modelling and imputation framework that accounts for and utilises Structured Missingness

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Thank you!

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